

Designing ships for extreme non-linear responses - the role of the acquisition function in the Adaptive Screening extreme value prediction method

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Abstract. The Adaptive Screening extreme value prediction method defined in [1] was applied to three cases, predicting most probable maximum values in a given duration. We used either Gaussian Process Regression (GPR) or its multi-fidelity form (MF-GPR) for the regression, and compared seven acquisition functions for the adaptive sampling. The results were judged based on several performance metrics, of which the required number of HF samples for convergence is the most important one. The results of this exercise show that the best option is to use Adaptive Screening with MF-GPR and an acquisition function that balances obtaining new samples around the probability of interest and the tail of the distribution. If the use of MF-GPR is not feasible for any reason, it should be replaced with GPR (or Generalised Pareto fitting) combined with an acquisition function that selects new samples based on the largest probability gap from the existing samples.

Key words: Extreme value prediction, Non-linear responses, Design loads, Hydrodynamics, Probabilistic design, Acquisition functions, Adaptive Sampling

1 Introduction and objectives

Designing marine and coastal structures for strongly non-linear responses such as wave impact loads is very challenging. Such responses are both complex and rare, so it is hard to predict their extreme values at a specified probability of exceedance. The rarity of the events requires long analysis durations, whereas the complexity requires high-fidelity (HF) modelling with CFD or experiments. Most existing methods are either suitable for weakly non-linear responses only, or too computationally demanding. The review of [2] discusses this in detail. For this reason, we developed the multi-fidelity ‘Adaptive Screening’ (AS) method, an extreme value prediction method for strongly non-linear responses (see pilot study in [3] and full method description with three case studies in [1]). Adaptive Screening combines elements of screening methods, adaptive sampling and Gaussian Process Regression (GPR).

The objective of the present paper is to evaluate the role of the acquisition function in the adaptive sampling part of the method. In [1], we used an acquisition function that directed sampling towards both the most uncertain regions of the HF exceedance probability distribution and its tail. Sampling was stopped once the distribution shape had converged. While this approach was effective, alternative sampling strategies may offer improved efficiency. Given the high computational cost of HF evaluations, it is important to minimise the number of such events. Therefore, this study aims to assess which sampling strategy achieves the desired extreme value accuracy with the fewest HF evaluations.

We briefly summarise the Adaptive Screening method from [1] in Section 2, and describe the considered acquisition functions in Section 3. The implementation of several acquisition functions is tested against two weakly non-linear case studies described in [1]: extreme value prediction of second-order wave crests (application 1, see Section 5.1) and of vertical bending moment (VBM) peaks on a ferry (application 2, see Section 5.2). The results and a discussion for both applications can be found in Section 6, and conclusions are drawn in Section 7. The most important nomenclature throughout the paper is summarised in Box 1.

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\bar{x}	Mean of variable x	$\mathbf{d}_L^{\text{sel}}$	PoE of selected LF peaks, increasing order
σ_x^2	Variance of variable x	H_s	Significant wave height
\hat{x}	MPM of variable x	\mathbf{h}^*	Predicted HF peak values over range \mathbf{d}^*
AS	Adaptive Screening	\mathbf{h}^{sel}	HF peak values in the selected events
CFD	Computational Fluid Dynamics	i	Number of iterations
GPR	Gaussian Process Regression	j	Number of HF samples
HF	High-Fidelity	$\mathbf{1}^{\text{mcs}}$	All LF peak values in the MCS, decreasing order
LF	Low-Fidelity	$\mathbf{1}^{\text{sel}}$	Selected LF peak values, decreasing order
MCS	Monte-Carlo Simulation	m	Number of initially selected HF samples
MF-GPR	Multi-Fidelity Gaussian Process Regression	n	Number of LF indicator peaks in the MCS
MPM	Most Probable Maximum	n_w	Number of wave encounters in the MCS
PoE	Probability of Exceedance	P_{exp}	PoE level corresponding to T_{exp} and wave period
USMV	Acquisition func. (uncertainty sampling + mean value)	T_{exp}	Target / exposure duration (typically 20min-3h)
C' or C''	LF or HF wave crest height	T_p	Peak wave period
\mathbf{d}^*	New PoE prediction range for HF, increasing order	$T_{p,e}$	Peak encounter wave period
$\mathbf{d}_H^{\text{sel}}$	Est. PoE of selected HF peaks, increasing order	V_s	Ship forward speed
$\mathbf{d}_L^{\text{mcs}}$	PoE of all LF peaks in the MCS, increasing order	V' or V''	LF or HF hogging vertical bending moment
		μ	Wave heading w.r.t. structure
		ω	Wave frequency

Box 1: Most important nomenclature.

Figure 1: Schematic illustration of Adaptive Screening, where the numbers roughly correspond to the method steps in [Appendix A.1](#). Modified reproduction from [\[1\]](#).

2 The Adaptive Screening method in brief

Adaptive Screening is a multi-fidelity method that can be used to predict extreme values of non-linear HF marine and coastal structure responses to waves. The idea of AS is briefly described below, and the important details and formulations from [\[1\]](#) are reproduced in [Appendix A](#). For the underlying ideas and assumptions, we refer to the earlier publication. [Figure 1](#) schematically illustrates the process. AS was designed to find HF extreme values with a target probability of exceedance (PoE), or equivalently a target return period. In [\[1\]](#), we focused on the most probable maximum (MPM) for a given exposure duration (typically 20 min to 3 hours, depending on ergodicity of the operating conditions at sea). The PoE corresponding to this duration is called P_{exp} .

AS uses a low-fidelity (LF) indicator variable, with order statistics that are correlated to those of the target HF response variable ([Step 1](#) in [Figure 1](#) and [Appendix A](#)). This indicator can be an LF version of the same variable or another variable with comparable order statistics, meaning that the LF response can reliably predict which wave events lead to large HF responses. We perform a long LF Monte-Carlo Simulation (MCS, [Step 2](#)) and identify all n indicator peaks and n_w wave crests ([Step 3](#)). The number of wave crests is the basis for all exceedance distributions (both LF and HF) made in AS. We then calculate the LF PoE distribution, relative to n_w ([Step 4](#)).

Next, a few initial wave events are selected around P_{exp} from this LF distribution ([Step 5](#)). The corresponding HF response is obtained by running a HF simulation for the selected wave events ([Step 6](#)). We

then use a critical assumption, that is also used in other screening methods: we assume that the PoE of the thus obtained HF responses is similar to that of the selected LF wave events. Obviously, this only works with a suitable indicator signal. The result of this is a sparsely populated HF PoE distribution, consisting only of the HF responses in the selected events (Step 7). This PoE distribution is a noisy representation of the real HF distribution. The next step is to use Gaussian Process Regression (GPR) to obtain a surrogate HF distribution over a given PoE range and its uncertainty, based on the noisy sparse HF distribution data of the previous steps (Step 8, Step 9). GPR can be used either in single-fidelity form (see e.g., [4]), or in multi-fidelity form (MF-GPR, see e.g., [5, 6]), where the LF and HF distribution shapes are used as input. From this surrogate HF distribution, we can estimate the target HF extreme value (Step 10).

Obviously, the result of this procedure will not be accurate when e.g., only 2-3 initial wave events are selected. AS therefore includes an adaptive sampling loop (Step 11). In each iteration, an acquisition function is applied to the predicted surrogate HF distribution to select an additional wave event. The present paper focuses on this acquisition function, as will be explained in Section 3. This process is repeated until convergence is reached according to a stopping criterion. We chose a stopping criterion that detects when the predicted PoE distributions no longer show significant changes (see Appendix A.2). The results of the converged procedure (Step 12) are the converged surrogate HF distribution over the defined range of PoE values, the associated extreme value (in our case the MPM value), and their uncertainty.

We use Python toolboxes GPy ([7], v1.10.0) and Emukit ([8], v0.4.9) to implement the (MF-)GPR formulations. The acquisition function and stopping criteria were newly implemented. All utilised scripts associated with the present study are available in the 4TU repository: [9].

3 Acquisition functions

In Step 11 of AS (following the steps defined in Figure 1 and appendix A.1), an acquisition function is used to guide the adaptive sampling. HF event calculations are costly for strongly non-linear responses, so this function should minimise the total number of required events. In the present study, we compare the performance of different acquisition functions. Each of them selects one new HF sample per iteration, even when used in combination with MF-GPR. For each iteration i , we define $p_{new,i}$ as the optimal PoE for adding a new LF sample to the existing set of selected samples \mathbf{d}_L^{sel} in Step 5.

We defined seven acquisition functions. Logical choices include selecting a new sample based on the largest local variance in the last iteration, minimising the total variance in the next step, guiding new samples towards the tail of the distribution or P_{exp} , or a weighted combination of these elements.

The first considered acquisition function, Uncertainty Sampling (US), places $p_{new,i}$ at the largest variance (or uncertainty) of the GPR prediction in the previous iteration. This is formulated in Equation (1), where $\bar{\mathbf{h}}^*$ is the mean surrogate HF prediction of the last iteration, $\sigma_{h^*}^2$ is its variance (both over prediction range \mathbf{d}^* , as explained in Appendix A) and we drop the iteration index i for convenience.

$$p_{new}^{us} = \arg \max [\sigma_{h^*}^2] \quad (1)$$

Secondly, we define the Maximum Value (MV) acquisition function in Equation (2). It only guides samples towards the tail of the distribution, regardless of the uncertainty of the prediction in the previous iteration.

$$p_{new}^{mv} = \arg \max [\bar{\mathbf{h}}^*] \quad (2)$$

Thirdly, we define the function USMV, which balances the US and MV functions as formulated in Equation (3). In [1] we used USMV for the validation cases.

$$p_{new}^{usmv} = \arg \max [\sigma_{h^*}^2 \cdot \bar{\mathbf{h}}^*] \quad (3)$$

Fourthly, we define the function USPD as the product of US and a normalised hill-parabola over \mathbf{d}^* (with elements d^*), with its maximum at P_{exp} . This is formulated in Equation (4). The parabola part of this acquisition function has high values close to P_{exp} , guiding samples in that direction. This function is useful when only the MPM value at the intersection with P_{exp} is relevant. It is likely less suitable when the overall shape of the distribution is also important.

$$p_{\text{new}}^{\text{uspd}} = \arg \max \left[\sigma_{h^*}^2 \cdot \left(\frac{f_2(d^*)}{\max(f_2(d^*))} \right) \right] \quad \text{where:} \quad \begin{cases} f_1(d^*) = 1 - (d^* - \ln(P_{\text{exp}}))^2 \\ f_2(d^*) = f_1(d^*) - \min(f_1(d^*)) \end{cases} \quad (4)$$

As a fifth acquisition function we make yet another combination: the product of MV in Equation (2) (focusing the samples on the tail of the distribution), and the hill-parabola described above (focusing the samples around P_{exp}). This is formulated in Equation (5), where f_1 and f_2 are defined in Equation (4).

$$p_{\text{new}}^{\text{mvpd}} = \arg \max \left[\mathbf{h}^* \cdot \left(\frac{f_2(d^*)}{\max(f_2(d^*))} \right) \right] \quad (5)$$

Since the indicator in AS is never perfect in practice, some deviation between the converged prediction and the true extreme value is inevitable. As shown in [1], this deviation can be sufficiently small for a range of realistic problems with varying degrees of non-linearity. However, the use of the LF indicator inherently introduces a noise-driven uncertainty band in the surrogate predictions, which tends to be relatively insensitive to the sample locations. This potentially limits the effectiveness of functions such as US and USMV. We therefore also consider a simpler function MD, which selects new samples based on the maximum distance (along the probability axis) from existing HF samples. As explained in Appendix A, the already available HF samples for the current iteration are written as $[\mathbf{d}_H^{\text{sel}}, \mathbf{h}^{\text{sel}}]$, with $\mathbf{d}_H^{\text{sel}} = \{h_1, h_2, \dots, h_m\}$ ordered such that $h_1 < h_2 < \dots < h_m$. The MD function is then formulated in Equation (6). The new point corresponds to the point located halfway between h_k and h_{k+1} , where the gap $h_{k+1} - h_k$ is the largest among all pairs of consecutive selected samples. Using MD would imply that the uncertainty band provided by (MF-)GPR is not strictly necessary. Simpler alternatives to single-fidelity GPR - such as fitting a Generalised Pareto distribution - could therefore be considered for surrogate regression. However, the combined use of LF and HF samples in MF-GPR may still provide additional benefits.

$$p_{\text{new}}^{\text{md}} = \arg \max_{k \in \{1, \dots, m-1\}} \left(\frac{h_{k+1} - h_k}{2} + h_k \right) \quad (6)$$

Finally, Integrated Variance Reduction (IVR) places the new sample such that the mean predicted variance in the next iteration is minimised [10]. This is similar to the expected improvement of the prediction used by e.g., [11]. This is formulated in Equation (7), where V_i is defined as the ‘integrated variance’ over the PoE prediction range \mathbf{d}^* (see Step 8 in Appendix A.1), and d^* are the PoE values in this range. In theory, IVR is an efficient choice to speed up convergence of the solution over the iterations, but it is also computationally expensive due to the iterative process required to calculate V_i .

$$p_{\text{new}}^{\text{ivr}} = \arg \max [V_i(d^*)] \quad \text{where:} \quad V_i(d^*) = \text{mean} \left(\frac{\text{cov}(d^*, d^{*'})^2}{\sigma_{h^*}^2} \right) \quad (7)$$

Independent of the acquisition function, the new $p_{\text{new},i}$ for iteration i is the optimal PoE for adding a new LF sample to the existing set of selected samples $\mathbf{d}_L^{\text{sel}}$ in Step 5. However, in AS, we can only use samples from the available LF MCS sample pool $\mathbf{d}_L^{\text{mcs}}$ of Step 4. We therefore always select the closest available sample from $\mathbf{d}_L^{\text{mcs}}$ to $p_{\text{new},i}$, without replacement (see Equation (8)). The new sample $d_{L,i}$ is added to $\mathbf{d}_L^{\text{sel}}$ in iteration i . It may be more efficient to select multiple samples per iteration, as the HF event simulations can be performed in parallel, but this is not considered in the present study.

$$d_{L,i} = \left[\arg \min_{d \in \mathbf{d}_L^{\text{mcs}}} |p_{\text{new},i} - d| \right] \quad (8)$$

4 Performance metrics

The performance of AS can be judged based both on its efficiency and its accuracy. The selected performance metric for the efficiency M_1 is the number of HF samples required to reach convergence (as defined by the stopping criterion in Appendix A.2).

The selected performance metrics for accuracy are the deviation of the MPM prediction from the ground truth at convergence, and the deviation of the shape of the distribution from the ground truth at convergence. For each iteration, we obtain a distribution prediction of the general form shown in the right pane of [Figure 1](#). From this we derive the MPM using [Equation \(A.5\)](#). The related performance metric M_2 is given in [Equation \(9\)](#), where \widehat{H}_t is the ground truth MPM and $\widehat{H}(i)$ the MPM predicted in iteration i . M_2 therefore describes the MPM deviation at convergence. For the distribution metric M_3 we use a similar formulation to the second part of the stopping criterion in [Appendix A.2](#). This is also formulated in [Equation \(9\)](#), where \mathbf{h}_t^* is the ground truth distribution and $\mathbf{h}^*(i)$ is the predicted distribution in iteration i , both defined over prediction range PoE values \mathbf{d}^* . M_3 therefore describes the maximum distribution deviation (at any probability level) at convergence.

$$M_2(i) = \frac{|\widehat{H}(i) - \widehat{H}_t|}{\widehat{H}_t} \quad M_3(i) = \frac{\max |\mathbf{h}^*(i) - \mathbf{h}_t^*|}{\widehat{H}_t} \quad (9)$$

The lower all three metrics, the better the prediction. However, M_1 is most important, since the convergence criteria should take care of the accuracy of the prediction. M_2 and M_3 are then used to check whether the results converge towards the ground truth (and not towards a biased value). There will always be some bias in the procedure due to the use of the LF indicator, but this shouldn't be too large.

5 Applications

5.1 Application 1 (a, b)

Application 1 from [\[1\]](#) addresses a weakly non-linear problem involving the prediction of extreme values of second-order wave crest heights, for a long-crested steep JONSWAP wave spectrum with $H_s = 10$ m, $T_p = 11$ s, $\gamma = 3.3$ at 30 m water depth. The HF responses were second-order wave crests C'' . Two LF indicators were defined: linear Gaussian wave crests C''_{good} (indicator GoodInd, application 1a) and crests in the same linear Gaussian waves plus an additional ‘noise’ wave system C''_{worse} (indicator WorseInd, application 1b). For details of the selected LF MCS duration (50 hours), details of both indicators and further details of the test case and implementations, see the earlier publication. Since the HF responses are analytically tractable, generating long HF ground truth time traces was easy for this case. The goal was to predict the HF one-hour MPM value \widehat{C}'' , at $T_{\text{exp}} = 3600$ s. The probability of interest $P_{\text{exp}} = 3.06 \times 10^{-3}$ for this application follows from [Equation \(A.3\)](#), where $n_w \approx 1.64 \times 10^4$ is the approximate number of wave crests in the 50-hour MCS at zero forward speed (so $T_{p,e} = T_p$). The true HF one-hour MPM for the chosen 50-hour realisation was 10.56 m, with a mean of 10.55 m across the realisations and U95% uncertainty of 0.10 m.

The true LF and HF zero up-crossing peak PoE distributions for the 50-hour MCS are shown in [Figure 2](#). These LF distributions followed from [Step 3](#) of Adaptive Screening, and the HF distribution was generated similarly. To assess indicator quality, we matched LF and HF crest peaks over time by identifying LF zero up-crossing peaks and locating the maximum HF response within each LF interval. In this procedure, LF and HF peaks can still be matched when they are slightly shifted in time. The resulting scatter plot in [Figure 3](#) shows that the LF and HF crest statistics closely align, though not perfectly. Linear wave crests are a pretty good indicator for second-order wave crests, so this is logical. We chose two PoE levels in the initial sampling for [Step 5](#) of Adaptive Screening, 0.001 and 0.01 ($m = 2$), positioned around P_{exp} defined above. The prediction range \mathbf{d}^* in [Step 8](#) was selected between 5×10^{-4} and 2×10^{-2} in 200 uniform steps, containing 450 HF events. To generate a ‘new’ HF sample in each iteration, we used the matched LF and HF peaks as described above. When an event was selected based on its LF indicator value (in [Step 5](#) or [Step 11](#)), the corresponding HF value was drawn from the matched LF-HF peaks. This is only possible because we have an analytically traceable HF variable; in reality, each iteration would require a new HF event calculation. To monitor convergence, we set stopping criteria limits for $S(j)$ in [Equation \(A.9\)](#): $\epsilon_1 = 0.05$ m for the maximum absolute wave crest distribution difference, and $\epsilon_2 = 0.003$ for the coefficient of variation of the one-hour MPM value (standard deviation 0.3% of mean). For MF-GPR, we also need the LF distribution as input, for which we used a subset of the full LF MCS samples (for details, again refer to [\[1\]](#)).

Figure 2: Peak (or crest) distributions LF indicator and HF validation data; application 1a,b (left) and 2 (right).

Figure 3: Scatter of matched LF indicator and HF validation peaks (or crests); application 1a (left), 1b (middle) and 2 (right).

5.2 Application 2

Application 2 from [1] explores the moderately non-linear problem of predicting hogging vertical bending moments (VBM) on a 190 m ferry in extreme irregular head waves with a JONSWAP spectrum, $H_s = 13.2$ m, $T_p = 10.0$ s, $\gamma = 3.0$, at 10 knots speed (5.14 m/s). For further details of the case (loading condition, mesh, simulation tools, background of the selected forward speed and very steep wave condition), see the earlier publication. The HF response V'' was generated using a non-linear VBM simulation, while the LF indicator V' was generated using a linear simulation of the same VBM response. The hogging peaks were defined by the zero up-crossing troughs in these VBM simulations. Unlike in application 1, this HF response is not analytically tractable, but 30-hour MCS non-linear simulations were feasible. The goal was to predict the HF 30-minute MPM value \widehat{V}'' , at $T_{exp} = 1800$ s. The probability of interest $P_{exp} = 4.18 \times 10^{-3}$ for this application follows from Equations (A.1) and (A.3), where $T_{p,e} = 7.5$ s for $T_p = 10.0$ s at 5.14 m/s speed in head waves, and $n_w \approx 1.44 \times 10^4$ is the approximate number of wave crests in the 30-hour MCS. The true HF 30-minute MPM for the chosen 30-hour realisation was 1.05×10^9 Nm.

The true LF and HF zero up-crossing peak PoE distributions for the 30-hour MCS are shown in Figure 2. We matched the LF and HF VBM hogging peaks in the same way as described for the wave crests, resulting in the scatter plot in Figure 3. This shows that, as expected, the hogging LF indicator and HF response peaks have less similar order statistics than those of the wave crests in application 1. For the initial sampling in Step 5 we again chose two PoE levels (0.001 and 0.01) and for the prediction range in Step 8 we chose 1×10^{-3} to 5×10^{-2} with 200 uniform steps (both centered around P_{exp}). For each selected event, the corresponding HF value (determined by the LF indicator value in Step 5 or Step 11) was drawn from HF simulation database at the closest matching time. To monitor convergence (see Equation (A.9)), we limited the coefficient of variation of the MPM value to $\epsilon_2 = 0.003$ (standard deviation 0.3% of mean) and the

Figure 4: Application 1a (indicator GoodInd): performance of Adaptive Screening with GPR or MF-GPR and different acquisition functions to predict the mean second-order wave crest MPM value and its U95% uncertainty. Annotations indicate converged MPM accuracy.

maximum absolute distribution difference to $\epsilon_1 = 5 \times 10^6$ Nm (with maximum hogging peak values in the order of 1.5×10^9 Nm). A similar subset of the LF MCS samples as in application 1 was used as LF VBM input for MF-GPR.

6 Results and discussion

For all three applications (1a, 1b and 2) described in Sections 5.1 and 5.2, the goal is to predict the high-fidelity most probable maximum (MPM) value, as well as the shape of the PoE distribution around P_{exp} . In application 1a,b this is the 1-hour MPM second-order wave crest height \hat{C}'' ; in application 2 it is the 30-minute MPM non-linear hogging VBM \hat{V}'' . We applied Adaptive Screening with single- and multi-fidelity GPR and the seven acquisition functions defined in Section 3 to these cases until convergence was reached (according to Equation (A.9)). IVR is significantly more computationally expensive than the other functions, so this function was only combined with single-fidelity GPR.

The convergence of the predicted MPM values and its U95% uncertainty as a function of the number of samples can be found in Figure 4 for application 1a, in Figure 5 for application 1b, and in Figure 6 for application 2. These plots include an indication of the mean prediction accuracy at convergence for each function, and a reference line at the ground-truth MCS value. Note that j on the axis is defined as the total number of HF samples, which is equal to two initial samples plus the number of iterations i . The number of required samples for convergence (performance metric M_1 from Section 4) using each acquisition function is summarised in the top of Figure 7. Similar plots for the accuracy metrics M_2 (MPM deviation) and M_3 (maximum distribution shape deviation) are shown in the other parts of the figure.

Figures 4 to 6 show that the results from all acquisition functions converge to a similar MPM value per case (which is confirmed by M_2 in Figure 7). This converged value is not exactly identical to the MCS true value, but it is quite close (the mean deviations from the true MPM are below 2% for all cases, and the maximum deviations are all below 3%). This is inherent to the Adaptive Screening method; the indicator is never perfect, so the converged results will always have some deviation from the true values. However, the present results show that we can still predict quite accurate HF MPM values, even when the indicator is not perfect. This was discussed in more detail in [1].

Figure 5: Application 1b (indicator WorseInd): performance of Adaptive Screening with GPR or MF-GPR and different acquisition functions to predict the mean second-order wave crest MPM value and its U95% uncertainty. Annotations indicate converged MPM accuracy.

Figure 6: Application 2: performance of Adaptive Screening with GPR or MF-GPR and different acquisition functions to predict the mean hogging MPM value and its U95% uncertainty. Annotations indicate converged MPM accuracy.

M_1 in Figure 7 shows that in general, Adaptive Screening with MF-GPR is more efficient than with GPR, regardless of the acquisition function. This is the result of leveraging the LF distribution shape as well by MF-GPR. The LF and HF distribution shapes in the present applications are relatively similar, which makes this effect even stronger. For more non-linear cases the effect may be less pronounced. However, the LF and HF distributions need to have some similarity in order for the LF variable to be useful as an indicator. MF-GPR is therefore expected to always have an advantage over GPR in the context of Adaptive

Figure 7: Performance metrics M_1 (required number of samples for convergence), M_2 (MPM deviation) and M_3 (maximum distribution deviation) of all three cases.

Screening.

The results are considered converged at M_1 samples, but the predicted PoE distributions become quite stable with significantly fewer samples. That is important, as each HF sample requires an expensive HF event evaluation. Selecting a more lenient stopping criterion may reduce the required number of samples significantly.

We now compare the performance of the various acquisition functions. As shown by M_1 in Figure 7, the IVR function does not significantly accelerate convergence relative to other methods for the test cases considered. Given its substantially higher computational cost, IVR is not the best choice to use with Adaptive Screening. Our focus shifts to evaluating Adaptive Screening in combination with MF-GPR. The figure shows that the US approach, which selects points based on the uncertainty of the prediction, performed comparatively poorly for our cases, despite its widespread use in the literature. This is probably because the predicted uncertainty band in the Adaptive Screening context becomes rather uniform over the prediction range. Guiding samples towards the distribution tail (as done in MV) speeds up convergence of the MPM prediction compared to US. The results for the function that balances these two elements, USMV, are quite similar or slightly better than for MV only. While the MD function achieves similar M_1 values to US and USMV, its associated spreading is lower, indicating more consistent performance. The functions USPD and MVPD perform less well when combined with GPR, which is expected. These strategies direct samples toward P_{exp} , where the MPM is interpolated, resulting in a concentrated ‘cloud’ of samples around this PoE. Such clustering provides limited information about other PoE levels, and fitting a GPR model to this can lead to unrealistic distribution estimates, even though the MPM prediction is acceptable. However, when combined with MF-GPR, the MVPD function requires the fewest mean HF samples. The low M_3 values (maximum distribution deviation) in Figure 7 for MF-GPR with either MVPD or USPD indicate accurate distribution predictions. The ‘cloud fitting’ issue was avoided by leveraging the LF distribution shape with MF-GPR. This demonstrates that USPD and MVPD can be effective when used with MF-GPR. Since MVPD yields a slightly lower overall M_1 , we identify it as the preferred acquisition function.

Considering these results, the MVPD acquisition function combined with MF-GPR seems the best choice for the present applications. [Figure 8](#) shows the true and converged predicted distributions for this combination. These distributions also illustrate why the uncertainty of the wave crest predictions is much higher in application 1b (with indicator `WorseInd`) than in application 1a (with indicator `GoodInd`); the scatter in the HF samples is much higher with the worse indicator in 1b, resulting in a larger uncertainty band in the (MF-)GPR predictions. In the unlikely case that application of MF-GPR is not an option for some reason (e.g., unavailability of a working code or a very large dataset that renders MF-GPR very inefficient), GPR should not be combined with the USPD or MVPD functions. In that case, MD seems the best option. However, the combination GPR / MD can easily be replaced by the simpler regression procedure using a Generalised Pareto distribution combined with MD (as explained in [Section 3](#)).

These findings were based on weakly non-linear cases only, because there was sufficient validation material available for these cases. It is recommended to repeat the study for a strongly non-linear case, such as the wave impact loads that Adaptive Screening was designed for. In such a case, the similarity of the LF and HF data may be less, which in theory could highlight strong points of other acquisition functions. For more discussion and a pilot study that shows how Adaptive Screening could be applied to find design loads of strongly non-linear green water impact loads on a ship, we refer to [1].

The present application of adaptive sampling is quite specific, so the lessons learned from this study are not necessarily generalisable to other GPR-adaptive sampling applications. Firstly, this is because we apply (MF-)GPR directly to the shape of the PoE distribution, and formulated acquisition functions to focus on the tail of the distribution or a specific PoE. That could be translated to other types of HF surfaces (e.g., to a design point or area of interest), but care should be taken in the treatment of the logarithm we use on the y-axis in that case. Secondly, the true PoE distribution is expected to be relatively smooth; for less smooth or discontinuous HF surfaces, other acquisition functions (and GPR kernels) could be more suitable. Thirdly, our HF samples include some ‘noise’ introduced by the non-perfect indicator order statistics. The uncertainty band predicted by (MF-)GPR for our problem is therefore relatively large and relatively uniform. This probably influences the performance of the different acquisition functions (especially those that guide new samples based on the predicted uncertainty).

7 Conclusions

The results discussed above show that for the presented applications, the best option is to use Adaptive Screening with MF-GPR and acquisition function MVPD (or possibly USPD). In the unlikely case that using MF-GPR is not an option for some reason, it should be substituted by GPR (or Generalised Pareto fitting) combined with acquisition function MD (or possibly US). These conclusions are based on three cases with moderate levels of non-linearity; it is recommended to check these conclusions again for a strongly non-linear case.

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Data availability

The data and scripts underlying this publication are available in (or can be re-generated using) the 4TU repository: [9].

(a) Application 1a.

(b) Application 1b.

(c) Application 2.

Figure 8: Predicted HF distributions by Adaptive Screening with MF-GPR and acquisition function MVPD; LF distribution (left) and HF distribution (right).

Appendices

A Details Adaptive Screening

Below, the steps and formulations used in Adaptive Screening are briefly described (with numbers roughly corresponding to Figure 1). This is a shortened reproduction of the full description in [1].

A.1 Steps and formulations

Step 1 Define an LF indicator with a strong statistical relation to the target HF response, as would be done in a screening method. The indicator signal is not necessarily the same signal at a different fidelity level as the target HF response; it can also be another signal with similar order statistics as the target

HF response. [2] reviews suitable wave impact indicators.

- Step 2 Perform LF Monte-Carlo Simulations (MCS) for a large number N of wave seeds, each with the same duration T_{exp} . This T_{exp} is the duration for which the hydrodynamic response is expected to remain ergodic (roughly 0.25-3 h, depending on waves, speed, course changes etc.). The total MCS has to be significantly longer than T_{exp} to obtain converged extreme values (see e.g., [12, 13]). The total MCS duration T_{tot} follows from $T_{\text{tot}} = NT_{\text{exp}}$.
- Step 3 Identify all n peak-over-threshold LF indicator peaks within T_{tot} . Also find the number of zero up-crossing encountered wave crests n_w in T_{tot} , which can be estimated using $n_w \approx NT_{\text{exp}}/T_{p,e}$ if there is no wave record available. $T_{p,e}$ in this formulation is the peak wave encounter period, which is different from the peak wave period T_p if the ship has forward speed. They are related using wave frequency $\omega = 2\pi/T$ and Equation (A.1), where ω_e is the wave encounter frequency, V_s is the forward speed of the ship and μ is the wave heading with respect to the ship (π is head waves in the used sign convention). n_w is the basis for all distributions presented here, which enables us to use LF indicators and HF responses with a different number of peaks.

$$\omega_e = \omega - \omega^2 V_s \cos(\mu) / g \quad (\text{A.1})$$

- Step 4 Calculate the LF PoE for all indicator peaks $\mathbf{d}_L^{\text{mcs}} = \{d_{L,i}^{\text{mcs}} | i = 1, 2, \dots, n\}$, related to the number of wave encounters, by applying Equation (A.2). The largest LF indicator peak value has a PoE of $1/n_w$ and the smallest n/n_w . We now have an LF indicator peak PoE distribution $[\mathbf{d}_L^{\text{mcs}}, \mathbf{I}^{\text{mcs}}]$.

$$\mathbf{d}_L^{\text{mcs}} = P(\mathbf{I}^{\text{mcs}} \geq l) \cdot \frac{n}{n_w} \quad (\text{A.2})$$

- Step 5 Select initial samples from the LF MCS dataset of the previous step. The selected set is called $[\mathbf{d}_L^{\text{sel}}, \mathbf{I}^{\text{sel}}]$, where $\mathbf{d}_L^{\text{sel}} = \{d_{L,k}^{\text{mcs}} | k = 1, 2, \dots, m\}$ and $\mathbf{I}^{\text{sel}} = \{I_k^{\text{mcs}} | k = 1, 2, \dots, m\}$. Different sampling strategies can be used to determine these indices k . Here we select these events around the PoE corresponding to T_{exp} based on the LF MCS dataset: the ‘probability of interest’. This P_{exp} is given in Equation (A.3). We pick m PoE values that span a range around P_{exp} and call them $[p_1, p_2, \dots, p_m]$. Now we use Equation (A.4) to add the elements in $\mathbf{d}_L^{\text{mcs}}$ closest to these values to the selected set, and the corresponding elements from \mathbf{I}^{mcs} . The resulting selected set $[\mathbf{d}_L^{\text{sel}}, \mathbf{I}^{\text{sel}}]$ is a subset of the full available LF MCS set $[\mathbf{d}_L^{\text{mcs}}, \mathbf{I}^{\text{mcs}}]$.

$$P_{\text{exp}} = N/n_w \approx T_{p,e}/T_{\text{exp}} \quad (\text{A.3})$$

$$d_{L,k}^{\text{mcs}} = \left[\arg \min_{d \in \mathbf{d}_L^{\text{mcs}}} |p_k - d| \right] \text{ for } k = 1, 2, \dots, m \quad (\text{A.4})$$

- Step 6 Find the corresponding HF response for the wave events corresponding to $[\mathbf{d}_L^{\text{sel}}, \mathbf{I}^{\text{sel}}]$, by running CFD calculations or experiments for these selected events. This new dataset of HF samples is called $\mathbf{h}^{\text{sel}} = \{h_k | k = 1, 2, \dots, m\}$, here h is the HF non-linear response value for event k .
- Step 7 Estimate the sample HF distribution, by assuming that the order statistics of \mathbf{I}^{sel} and \mathbf{h}^{sel} are identical. In other words, we assume that HF value h_k in event k from Step 6 is equally likely as the selected LF value $d_{L,k}^{\text{mcs}}$ in the same event from Step 5. This is a critical screening assumption, stating that the HF distribution $[\mathbf{d}_H^{\text{sel}}, \mathbf{h}^{\text{sel}}]$ can be estimated using $\mathbf{d}_H^{\text{sel}} \approx \mathbf{d}_L^{\text{sel}}$. This only works if a suitable indicator signal is chosen in Step 1.
- Step 8 Define a range of PoE between 1 and 0 where you want to estimate the HF distribution \mathbf{h}^* . We select this prediction range \mathbf{d}^* between approximately a factor ten below and above P_{exp} , defined in high to low PoE order.
- Step 9 Construct the surrogate HF distribution over $\ln(\mathbf{d}^*)$. We use the logarithm to construct a surrogate that focuses on the tail of the HF distribution. The estimated HF distribution from Step 7 only contains a few samples. We apply 1D single- or multi-fidelity GPR to the available samples to construct the surrogate HF distribution \mathbf{h}^* (including uncertainty) over this range.

- With single-fidelity GPR, we use the HF sample dataset $[\ln(\mathbf{d}_H^{\text{sel}}), \mathbf{h}^{\text{sel}}]$ from [Step 7](#) as input.
- With multi-fidelity MF-GPR, we use the same HF sample dataset $[\ln(\mathbf{d}_H^{\text{sel}}), \mathbf{h}^{\text{sel}}]$ from [Step 7](#) as input, *and* LF dataset $[\ln(\mathbf{d}_L^{\text{mcs}}), \mathbf{I}^{\text{mcs}}]$ from [Step 3](#). We used the linear autoregressive (AR1) multi-fidelity model with two levels [\[5\]](#).

We used Matern32 kernels. As it will not be possible to define a perfect indicator for most non-linear response problems, the HF sample data set $[\ln(\mathbf{d}_H^{\text{sel}}), \mathbf{h}^{\text{sel}}]$ will be ‘noisy’. To avoid overfitting and to ensure a monotonic distribution, we constrained the noise variance and length-scale hyperparameter in (MF-)GPR with lower limits. Details of the (MF-)GPR formulations and constraints are in [\[1\]](#). The result of the procedure is the HF prediction $[\ln(\mathbf{d}^*), \mathbf{h}^*]$. To avoid confusion, we emphasise that the regression model is linear and Gaussian, not the underlying HF process itself; we still predict extreme values of strongly non-linear responses.

Step 10 Estimate the target short-term extreme value from the (MF-)GPR prediction. Our target is the HF MPM value \hat{H} , found using [Equation \(A.5\)](#). The uncertainty of the MPM can be derived from the predicted GPR uncertainty band in the same way. This is illustrated by the horizontal line in the right inset of [Figure 1](#).

$$\mathbf{d}^*(\hat{H}) = P_{\text{exp}} \quad , \text{ therefore: } \hat{H} = \mathbf{d}^{*-1}(P_{\text{exp}}) \quad (\text{A.5})$$

Step 11 Start adaptive sampling, iterating over [Step 5](#) to [Step 11](#). In each iteration, an acquisition function is applied to define a new sample, unless convergence is reached. As we already guided the prediction in [Step 8](#) (by choosing a prediction range) and [Step 9](#) (by focusing on the tail of the distribution using the logarithm of PoE), we selected an adaptive strategy focusing on exploration rather than exploitation (see e.g., [\[14\]](#)). The new samples are selected from $[\mathbf{d}_L^{\text{mcs}}, \mathbf{I}^{\text{mcs}}]$ defined in [Step 4](#), without replacement. The required formulations are discussed in [Section 3](#) (the different considered acquisition functions) and [Appendix A.2](#) (stopping criterion). When a new HF sample is defined as discussed there, it is added to the LF selected set $[\mathbf{d}_L^{\text{sel}}, \mathbf{I}^{\text{sel}}]$ in [Step 5](#), after which [Step 6](#) to [Step 11](#) are repeated.

Step 12 When convergence is reached according to the criterion, the result is the converged prediction for the HF distribution \mathbf{h}^* over prediction range \mathbf{d}^* , the associated MPM value \hat{H} , and their uncertainty.

A.2 Stopping criterion

Below we summarise the stopping criterion applied in AS for the adaptive sampling. For more background of this criterion, we refer to [\[1\]](#). We set an acceptance criterion that requires the PoE distribution to decrease monotonically, with higher values at low PoE than at high PoE. Prediction range \mathbf{d}^* in [Step 8](#) is defined in ascending PoE order (first element of HF prediction \mathbf{h}^* is highest, last lowest). An iteration was rejected if it did not meet the acceptance criterion R in [Equation \(A.6\)](#) (where $w = \text{len}(\overline{\mathbf{h}}^*(j))$): each element of $\overline{\mathbf{h}}^*(j)_i$ must be smaller than the previous one, and the difference between the first and last elements must exceed 1% of the first element’s value.

$$R(j) = \begin{cases} \text{accept} & \text{if } [\forall i \in [2, \dots, w], \overline{\mathbf{h}}^*(j)_{i-1} > \overline{\mathbf{h}}^*(j)_i] \cap [\overline{\mathbf{h}}^*(j)_1 - \overline{\mathbf{h}}^*(j)_w > 0.01\overline{\mathbf{h}}^*(j)_1] \\ \text{reject} & \text{otherwise} \end{cases} \quad (\text{A.6})$$

Secondly, we calculated the maximum absolute difference $E(j)$ in HF value between each set of subsequently predicted distributions, averaged over the last K_1 iterations: $\overline{E}_{K_1}(j)$. When $j < K_1$, all available iterations were used.

$$\overline{E}_{K_1}(j) = \frac{1}{\psi} \sum_{i=\chi}^j E(i) \quad \text{where: } \begin{cases} E(j) = \max |\mathbf{h}^*(j) - \mathbf{h}^*(j-1)| \\ \chi = 1 \text{ and } \psi = j & \text{for } j = 1, 2, \dots, K_1 - 1 \\ \chi = j - K_1 + 1 \text{ and } \psi = K_1 & \text{for } j \geq K_1 \end{cases} \quad (\text{A.7})$$

A third convergence criterion was based on the coefficient of variation (COV) of the MPM value over the last K_2 iterations: $C_{K_2}(j)$. This is expressed in [Equation \(A.8\)](#), where $\hat{H}(j)$ is the MPM value predicted in iteration j . Again, we took the COV over the available iterations when $j < K_2$.

$$C_{K_2}(j) = \frac{\sigma_{K_2}(j)}{\mu_{K_2}(j)} \quad \text{where:} \quad \begin{cases} \mu_{K_2}(j) = \frac{1}{\psi} \sum_{i=\chi}^j \widehat{H}(i) \\ \sigma_{K_2}(j) = \sqrt{\frac{1}{\psi} \sum_{i=\chi}^j \left(\widehat{H}(i) - \mu_{K_2}(i) \right)^2} \\ \chi = 1 \text{ and } \psi = j & \text{for } j = 1, 2, \dots, K_2 - 1 \\ \chi = j - K_2 + 1 \text{ and } \psi = K_2 & \text{for } j \geq K_2 \end{cases} \quad (\text{A.8})$$

The total stopping criterion $S(j)$ is provided in Equation (A.9), where limits ϵ_1 and ϵ_2 are case-dependent, and where $K_1 = K_2 = 20$ balance limiting the influence of outliers and the minimum number of iterations for which convergence can be detected.

$$S(j) = \begin{cases} \text{stop} & \text{if } (R(j) = \text{accept}) \cap (\overline{E}_{20}(j) < \epsilon_1) \cap (C_{20}(j) < \epsilon_2) \\ \text{continue} & \text{otherwise} \end{cases} \quad (\text{A.9})$$

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